

On the durability of secondary PLA after use and multiple reprocessing iterations

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates, for the first time, the combined effects of aging and reprocessing on the mechanical and physicochemical properties of additively manufactured (AM) polylactic acid (PLA), simulating service life. A methodology was developed that integrates accelerated aging - through weathering and hygrothermal conditions - with mechanical recycling via filament extrusion for remanufacturing by AM. Mechanical and viscoelastic degradation was assessed using tensile and dynamic mechanical analysis, while the underlying physicochemical mechanisms were examined by Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC), X-ray Computed Tomography (CT), and optical microscopy. Property evolution was tracked over four iterative cycles of aging followed by reprocessing (multiple-use scenario) and compared with single-use aging. Results show that hygrothermal aging induced more severe deterioration than weathering across all properties. After four cycles, tensile strength and strain at break decreased by more than 50 %, mainly due to hydrolytic scission of ester bonds. Reprocessing alone lowered molecular weight and strain at break but had only a minor effect on secondary carbonyl formation. In multiple-use scenarios, the combined action of aging and reprocessing produced a synergistic degradation, where thermo-mechanical stresses accelerated chain scission and property loss. These findings demonstrate the critical influence of coupled degradation mechanisms on the recyclability potential of AM-PLA, offering valuable insights for the polymer industry in enhancing recycled content in new plastic products, without compromising performance.

1. Introduction

In recent years, with the global motivation of moving towards a circular economy, plastic recycling and the use of recycled plastics have become an emerging and growing trend for many industrial applications [1,2]. As reported in 2022 by ‘Plastic Recyclers Europe’, the total installed recycling capacity in Europe represented 12.5 MT, more than double compared to 2017, with the expectation of reaching 16 MT in 2025 and 20 MT in 2030 [1]. Even if today, still only 10 % of the total plastic produced in Europe is being recycled, this number is expected to grow rapidly, given the strict ongoing European Commission (EC) measures [1,2]. This significant increase in the number of recycled plastics is expected to present new challenges to the industry and governmental authorities, requiring the ability to utilise recycled plastic (secondary raw material or ‘recyclates’) in new products without compromising performances.

In parallel to classical fossil-derived polymers, bio-based thermo-plastics are an increasingly important area of interest within circular economy strategies. Derived from renewable feedstocks, these biodegradable materials are typically characterised by reduced carbon footprints. However, for them to be entirely exploited within material circular loops, their recyclability must also be addressed and optimised accordingly. Although composting is an established end-of-life (EoL) disposal method for most bio-based plastics, mechanical recycling has now become a preferred route in the quest for material recovery and reduced energy input [2,22,25]. This disparity between recyclability and biodegradability is a critical area for future research on sustainable plastics.

Recently, growing concerns over environmental sustainability have led to the exploration of alternative materials for various engineering applications. One such material is Polylactic Acid (PLA), a biodegradable and bio-based thermoplastic that offers a reduced carbon footprint

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and the potential to replace conventional petroleum-based plastics in various industries [3–6]. Considering its mechanical properties, low environmental impact, and good processability, PLA is expected to exhibit remarkable growth in the market in the coming years, particularly in the field of Additive Manufacturing (AM). Although PLA is biodegradable under industrial composting conditions [7], a recent focus has been on its recyclability, as a complementary or alternative end-of-life strategy. Mechanical recycling of PLA has been demonstrated to be technically viable and is supported by significant advantages in terms of energy use and carbon footprint [2,8,9]. While composting leads to the release of CO₂ and offers little to no material recovery, mechanical recycling reduces the need for virgin PLA production while retaining material integrity. For instance, the energy demand of PLA mechanical recycling is approximately two times lower than composting, and greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions are likewise reduced [10]. Thus, mechanical recycling of PLA leads to energy savings and lower greenhouse gas emissions.

While PLA -as well as other polymers-is biodegradable and recyclable, it is known that recycling as a process significantly degrades plastic material properties [11–13]. An example is recycled Polyethylene terephthalate (PET), which presents, after recycling, shorter chain lengths and oxidised chemical groups, leading to a more brittle polymer with reduced viscosity and elasticity [12,14]. Similarly, Gustavo Barbosa et al. reported a decrease to 86.53 % in impact resistance values of Polypropylene (PP) after secondary recycling, in comparison with virgin PP [11]. Besides the recycling process, when considering the use phase (lifetime) of plastics, the different service environments impact material properties in the long term, through various degradation mechanisms [15–19]. Several studies have focused on tailored accelerated aging, investigating the evolution of properties after exposure to, e.g. UV radiation, thermal and hygrothermal environments [14–16,20–22]. On this, Panowicz, R. et al. have reported that 35 days of thermo-oxidative aging of PET leads to an increase in Glass Transition temperature values (T_g), explained by the crosslinking and chain scission due to thermo-oxidative reaction, also leading to a rise in stiffness values and a decrease in elongation at break values [23]. Similar observations have been reported for Polylactic Acid (PLA) [24,60] and PP [25–27], after accelerated aging and natural aging for varying periods. Thus, it is evident that both recycling and environmental aging deteriorate the original properties of polymers.

To understand the degradation processes of PLA, it is essential to consider the different mechanisms, each linked explicitly to external factors. Generally, polymers undergo physical and chemical degradation when subjected to hygrothermal aging. The degradation of a polymer in an aqueous environment is mainly controlled by the water uptake of the polymer, which is directly linked to its chemical structure. Polymers containing polar chemical functions are generally susceptible to degradation due to hygrothermal aging and will experience diminished properties over time when exposed to an aqueous environment. The temperature of the environment, as well as the sample thickness, are also parameters influencing the polymer's degradation, in line with water diffusion into the material and based on the second Fick's law [19,28,29]. Specifically for PLA, its degradation in water involves a non-enzymatic chain scission followed by a chain-end cleavage, leading to a decrease in its molecular weight (*M_w*) [7,30,31]. The degradation can also occur through the chain scission of leading chains, side chains, or intersectional chains [4]. The scission of the ester bond is a common feature in most PLA degradation mechanisms. Moreover, structural changes during the degradation process, including chain scission and crosslinking, can result in different degradation kinetics at various stages, therefore influencing further degradation processes [32,33]. In general, the hydrolysis of PLA can be described in several steps: water sorption, reduction of mechanical properties, decrease in molecular weight, and complete loss of material weight. [34,35]. The degradation process involves the diffusion of water molecules, starting in amorphous regions and subsequently initiating ester bond cleavage [5]. After

exposure to moisture, the ester groups of the main chain of PLA are cleaved, resulting in a decrease in molecular weight [33].

Accelerated weathering aging encompasses various variables, including UV irradiation over specific wavelengths, thermal aging, and exposure to moisture. The combination of UV radiation, elevated temperature, and higher relative humidity significantly reduces the mechanical properties of polymers, especially those of PLA, and accelerates its degradation. As a general rule, photodegradation of polymers under UV radiation involves chain-scission, backbone modification, and photo-oxidative crosslinking [36–38], leading to discolouration and brittle fracture, with a decrease in the mechanical properties [4,39]. Jeon and Kim reported that UV irradiation enhances PLA degradation by increasing the material's hydrophilicity, enabling easier water absorption by the polymer structures [16]. Foreman et al. [40] reported that accelerated weathering with UV irradiation and water spray at 50 °C for varying durations resulted in a deteriorated surface texture, discolouration, surface softness and cracks. Mechanical properties were also affected, revealing a reduction in tensile strength, flexural strength, Young's modulus, and flexural modulus values, attributed to plasticization, swelling effects, and photochemical degradation [22]. UV light exposure deteriorates the physical integrity of PLA, increases stress at break, and reduces its average molecular weight (*M_w*), thereby increasing its brittleness [41]. Additionally, a rapid decrease in *M_w* values (within 1 h) was reported after aging by Bocchini et al. [42]. The oxidation of the polymeric structure supports the decrease in mechanical properties, primarily studied through the evolution of the Carbonyl Index, which highlights the generation of carbonyl groups through the breakage of previously existing bonds [20]. According to the literature, the primary photodegradation mechanism of aliphatic polyesters (e.g. PET, PLA) follows Norrish-type photocleavage involving photoionisation (Norrish type I), succeeded by polymer chain scission (Norrish type II) [4]. This mechanism can also result in crosslinking reactions or oxidative processes [43].

In addition to the effect of service conditions, the thermal stability of PLA brings other challenges, especially when it comes to its recycling. Specifically, PLA degrades thermally during reprocessing, especially when using an extrusion system that involves mechanical forces at temperatures higher than its melting point (i.e., >190 °C) [44]. This effect is primarily attributed to the thermally unstable ester groups present in PLA, which are partially responsible for polymer degradation [5]. Various other factors can influence the thermal degradation of PLA, such as moisture and the presence of oxygen. Still, its degradation is also related to the residence time in the extruder [45]. Structural changes in PLA material can be identified by changes in the T_m values, which fluctuate between 159 °C and 178 °C, depending on the average molecular weight of the PLA material [46]. McNeal and Leiper [47] reported that thermal degradation predominantly occurs by random chain scission. This phenomenon can be intensified by extending the exposure time, increasing the exposure temperature, or applying mechanical stresses [48]. In the same work, authors stated that reprocessing PLA leads to thermal degradation, resulting in a rapid loss of molecular weight and, consequently, a loss in mechanical properties. Another study found that the thermo-oxidative degradation of PLA at an average processing temperature (approximately 200 °C) follows a random chain scission mechanism, resulting in significant molecular degradation and the formation of various degradation products [49]. The authors also reported that the thermal degradation of acetaldehyde occurs above 230 °C, resulting in different degradation mechanisms. On another note, Pillin et al. [50] investigated the behaviour of PLA with up to 7 cycles of recycling and reported that stiffness remained unaffected after thermo-mechanical cycling. In contrast, a significant decrease was noted in strength and rheological properties. The decline in strength was attributed to a substantial reduction in molecular weight resulting from synergistic degradation mechanisms.

In an ideal closed-loop circular economy, plastics are iteratively recycled/upcycled at their End-of-Life (EoL) into secondary raw

Table 1
Mean virgin material's properties [51].

Properties	Characterization method	Value	Unit
Density	Immersion method following the ISO 1183-1	1,24	g/cc
Ultimate Tensile Strength	Tensile test following the ISO 527	58	MPa
Tensile Modulus	Tensile test following the ISO 527	2870	MPa
Strain at break	Tensile test following the ISO 527	8	%
Glass Transition Temperature	Differential Scanning Calorimetry	55–60	°C

materials for the same or another application, without a decrease in their physico-mechanical properties. However, as mentioned previously, plastics are prone to degradation due to recycling and to service conditions during use. While several studies have individually examined the response of different polymers to service aging and recycling, the understanding of their combined impact remains elusive. Therefore, this work seeks to unravel potential synergistic effects and cumulative degradation patterns, as well as their impact on material, mechanical, and physico-chemical performance, with a focus on PLA. The study design replicates a real-world scenario where a polymer is service-aged during its use, and then mechanically recycled at its EoL stage. To do so, cycles of accelerated aging and reprocessing were realised in a laboratory setting. For accelerated aging, hygrothermal aging, and weathering were employed. For the reprocessing, the EoL phase has been simulated employing lab-scale mechanical recycling (grinding).

As such, two *Scenarios* were designed in this work:

- **Scenario 1: Single use:** Continuous accelerated aging to simulate the service environment to which a polymer is subjected to.
- **Scenario 2: Multiple uses:** Four iterative cycles of accelerated aging and reprocessing to simulate the lifetime of a plastic that is used, recycled and remanufactured.

The main goal is to outline both the physico-chemical mechanisms behind the degradation processes alongside the rate of property degradation occurring throughout the different processing scenarios. To do so, mechanical properties and viscoelastic properties were monitored through tensile testing and Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA), while the evolution in physicochemical properties was studied via Fourier-Transform-Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR), Gel-Permeation Chromatography (GPC), X-Ray Computed Tomography (CT-scanning) and Optical Microscopy. To the authors' knowledge, this is the first study investigating the combined impact of degradation due to service life and degradation due to reprocessing during EoL.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

In this work, Add:north Easy PLA filament (PLA Black Economy Serie – diameter 1,75 mm) was employed. Table 1 presents the mean virgin material properties of the material used to manufacture the coupons of this study.

2.2. Simulation of the reprocessing cycle: experimental procedure

As mentioned previously, for reprocessing, mechanical recycling was performed through grinding, followed by filament extrusion and sample (re)manufacturing using the FFF AM process.

The grinding process was realised using a tabletop grinder (SHR3D IT, 3D Evo B.V., Utrecht, The Netherlands). The process is based on grinding plastic through metallic blades, which apply both compressive and shear forces, resulting in flakes of approximately 8 mm diameter. The ground material was later dried at 60 °C for 24 h, before filament

Table 2
Printing parameters and their justifications.

Parameter	Value	Justification
Nozzle temperature	215 °C	Afrivianto et al. [53] reported that for PLA specimens, a nozzle temperature of 215 °C provides a printed material with a higher Young's modulus and a higher Ultimate Tensile Strength (UTS).
Infill density	100 %	According to Kechagias et al. [54], the use of a 100 % infill may provide the highest tensile strength and might avoid failure due to the sample structure more than to the material itself.
Printing Speed	40 mm/s	Studying the impact of the printing speed between 30 and 50 mm/s on the mechanical properties of PLA/30 % wood, Kechagias et al. highlighted a decrease in the UTS with the increased printing speed [55].
Layer thickness	0.15 mm	João Araújo Afonso and Jorge Lino Alves [56] showed an increase in the mechanical strength when decreasing the layer thickness. The thickness was chosen as a compromise between the printing time and mechanical properties.
Raster Deposition Angle	45°	It is reported in the literature that higher mechanical properties are obtained with a deposition angle near 0° [53]. In our case, after performing pre-tests, an angle of 0° showed bad appearance quality.
Bed Temperature	55 °C	The bed temperature was chosen to be inferior to the glass transition temperature [57], avoiding any physical change during the printing.

extrusion [52]. Filament extrusion was realised with a 3D Evo Composer 450 (3D Evo B.V., Utrecht, The Netherlands). For FFF AM, a Prusa i3 MK3S+ (Prusa Research a.s., Czech Republic) was employed. The printing parameters of the study were selected following previous works, as presented in Table 2.

Test coupons for tensile and DMA testing were manufactured according to the standards ISO 527-2 and ISO 6721-1, respectively. Fig. 1 depicts representative images of printed samples after manufacturing, recorded with Optical microscopy and with X-Ray Computed Tomography (CT-scanning), illustrating surface (Fig. 1a and b) and inherent morphological characteristics (Fig. 1c and d).

The two *Scenarios* designed to study the impact of service aging vs. the impact of reprocessing are schematically illustrated in Fig. 2.

Scenario 1 (Single-use) was developed to simulate the life of a polymer used for a specified period (not subjected to reprocessing). In this case, the initial filament (virgin material) was used to produce coupons via FFF, which were then tested to assess their initial mechanical and chemical properties. The coupons were aged in an accelerated manner, for a total of 60 days of aging, having 4 test intervals (every 15 days), simulating the useful life of the material.

Scenario 2 (Multiple use and reprocessing) was developed to simulate four iterative lives of a polymer used for a period of time and then iteratively recycled (four times) until complete degradation. Each use interval was simulated using accelerated aging for 15 days, while EoL was simulated using mechanical grinding and FFF AM for remanufacturing. It is worth mentioning that no virgin material was introduced, allowing for the use of only recycled material in a closed-loop system. During every reprocessing and aging interval, the entire amount of the material was recycled to ensure homogeneity among the samples and to maintain similar degradation levels. In *Scenario 2*, the coupons were tested after the initial manufacturing process to evaluate the initial properties of the samples and then tested after each cycle of aging and reprocessing to study the individual impact of both degradation factors.

2.3. Accelerated aging

To activate the Norrish I-II and cross-linking reactions, hygrothermal and weathering aging procedures were employed.

Fig. 1. PLA coupon after manufacturing - Microscope and CT-scan images.

Fig. 2. Schematic representation of Scenarios 1 & 2, to assess the impact of aging and reprocessing on the properties of the PLA polymer.

2.3.1. Hygrothermal aging

Hygrothermal aging was realised by immersing coupons in a stirred water tank (Grant GD120, Grant Instrument Europe, Amsterdam, The Netherlands) at a constant temperature of 40 °C for 15 days per cycle, filled with distilled water. The aging temperature was chosen based on the literature and results of hydrolytic degradation of PLA in diverse conditions (with a focus on aging performed at 30-40-50 °C). The aim

was to select a temperature accelerating degradation sufficiently for quantifiable analysis within a reasonable timeframe, while remaining low enough to avoid excessive degradation that could hinder the reprocessing of the material [21,24,58]. As an example, Orellana-Barrasa et al. studied in 2022 the hydrolytic degradation of PLA in water at temperatures between 20 and 80 °C and reported that 39 °C was the most effective aging temperature, far enough from the Tg

Fig. 3. Evolution of the material's appearance for both Scenarios 1 & 2 and environmental aging conditions.

to avoid physical changes and allowing quantification of the changes with paced degradation [21].

2.3.2. Weathering

Photothermal and moisture erosion cycles were employed to simulate accelerated weathering. For this purpose, a QUV weathering tester (Q-Lab Corporation, Westlake, USA) was used, equipped with a UVA 340 nm lamp as required by ASTM D4329-99 (Standard Practice for Fluorescent UV Exposure of Plastics).

Each aging cycle was programmed for a duration of 43200 s (12 h), including:

- 28800 s (8 h) of UVA exposure at 45 °C with an intensity of 0,89 W/m²
- 14400 s (4 h) of condensation in dark conditions at 40 °C

The duration of each cycle was chosen according to the standard ASTM D4329-99, whereas the temperatures were selected to be below the T_g of PLA (50–60 °C), according to Refs. [24,59], to avoid unwanted and unrealistic physico-chemical changes [60]. For the aging samples, metallic sheets were used, positioned without overlap to ensure an even distance between the sample surface and the UV lamps and spray nozzles.

2.4. Testing methodology

The assessment of the response of the material to aging and reprocessing was based on the quantification of mechanical and physico-chemical properties, involving (1) tensile testing, (2) Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA), (3) Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FT-IR) and (4) Gas Permeation Chromatography (GPC).

For both Scenarios, test results are presented after each testing interval. In the case of Scenario 1, the coupons were tested every 30 cycles (approximately 15 days) during the continuous aging process. In the case of Scenario 2, the coupons were tested at the end of each aging period (30 cycles (15 days)) and after each reprocessing step, which was repeated up to 4 times. However, in the case of hygrothermal aging, no data are presented after the 4th reprocessing cycle, as the material exhibited low processability and no testing coupons were obtained.

2.4.1. Material testing

2.4.1.1. Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA). DMA testing was employed to study the evolution of the viscoelastic properties of the material throughout aging and reprocessing cycles, allowing for the determination of the viscoelastic properties and specifically, alterations in the values of the Glass Transition temperature (T_g). DMA testing was performed using the DMA 850 (TA Instruments, New Castle, USA) in

Single Cantilever Beam mode, adapted for characterising high-damping materials. The tests were performed in oscillation–temperature ramp, between ambient temperature and 95 °C (at atmospheric pressure) with a temperature gradient of 5 °C/min. The oscillation was applied with an amplitude of 30,0 μ m at a frequency of 1.0 Hz. T_g values were determined from the maximum peak value of the $\text{Tan}(\delta)$ curve, indicating the onset of significant molecular chain mobility associated with the glass transition [61]. For each test interval, batches of 3 samples were analysed. The average T_g value and its associated standard deviation were plotted as a function of aging time and the number of reprocessing cycles.

2.4.1.2. Tensile testing. To determine the Young's modulus (E), ultimate strength (σ_{UTS}), and strain at break (ϵ_b) values of PLA coupons as a function of aging and reprocessing iterations, uniaxial tensile testing was performed. These tests were performed per ISO 527-2, using specimen type 1B. The specimen had an overall length of 150 mm, a width at the narrow portion of 10 mm, a length of the narrow parallel-sided portion of 60 mm, a thickness of 4 mm, and a gauge length of 50 mm. The tests were performed on an Instron 5966 (Instron, Norwood, USA) at a loading rate of 5 mm/min, with a load cell capacity of 10 kN, and an initial distance between grips of 115 mm. An AVE2 video-extensometer was used to record mechanical strain readings. For each testing interval, batches of 5 samples were characterised, and the average value and standard deviation were plotted as a function of aging time and reprocessing cycles.

2.4.1.3. Fourier Transform Infrared (FT-IR). FTIR testing was conducted on tensile coupons. The chemical changes were studied as a function of aging time and the number of reprocessing cycles using an FTIR spectrometer (Spectrum 3, PerkinElmer, Waltham, USA), equipped with a diamond Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR) accessory. FTIR scans were performed in the wavelength range of 4000–600 cm^{-1} , using 32 scans and a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} , to ensure a sufficient signal-to-noise ratio. An average of 3–5 different coupons was analysed, examining various areas of each sample. An internal normalisation was realised using the band at 1450 cm^{-1} , corresponding to the C-H stretching in the methyl groups, not expected to evolve during PLA degradation [30,62, 63].

Particular attention was paid to the carbonyl region (1745–1754 cm^{-1}), where changes in absorbance are widely used to monitor polymer oxidation and degradation. This band is generally attributed to C=O stretching in ester groups, but its evolution in PLA can also indicate the formation of secondary carbonyl species (e.g., carboxylic acids, aldehydes, or ketones) resulting from hydrolytic chain scission [34, 51, 77]. Although an increase or splitting in this band may suggest the presence of aldehyde groups, we acknowledge that this assignment should be interpreted with caution, as this region overlaps with several carbonyl-

Fig. 4. Internal structure evolution of the samples for both Scenarios 1 & 2 and environmental aging conditions.

Fig. 5. Storage modulus and Tan delta curves for Scenario 1 & 2 for both environmental aging conditions.

containing species.

2.4.1.4. *Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC)*. The molecular weight evolution of polymers during degradation is a widely used parameter to enhance the understanding of the polymer structure. The molecular weight is determined by the average molecular weight M_n and the weight-average molecular weight M_w . The evolution of the molecular weight distribution values was evaluated and studied as a function of the aging time and the number of reprocessing cycles.

3. Results and discussion

In both *Scenarios*, it was evident that accelerated aging and reprocessing caused colour changes that were visible to the naked eye. Specifically, colour evolution was observed on coupons subjected to

weathering for 45 days of aging (*Scenario 1*), and to a lesser degree for the case of *Scenario 2*. The printing quality also changed with aging and reprocessing, resulting in the production of samples with surface inconsistencies and defects. Fig. 3 illustrates the evolution of the material's appearance during experimentation, which is consistent with previous works [64].

Apart from appearance evolution during aging, the internal structure and quality of the samples also evolved, especially in the case of *Scenario 2* involving reprocessing cycles. Fig. 4 illustrates these changes, highlighting the presence of manufacturing voids after reprocessing cycles for both aging conditions, as well as the 'melted' parts of the samples in the case of *Scenario 1*. It is essential to highlight that changes in the mechanical properties studied later on in this study might be linked to the material degradation as well as to its structure evolution; however, itself linked to the material degradation.

Fig. 6. Glass transition temperature values evolution for both Scenarios 1 & 2 and environmental aging conditions.

3.1. Glass transition temperature evolution

The T_g value of a polymer is closely linked to its molecular structure and serves as an excellent indicator of its degradation. The T_g value can be influenced by the relative rigidity of the backbone chain of the polymer, the side groups, the chemical nature and size of the side groups, as well as the monomer structure and polymer mass [21]. Fig. 5 presents the Tan delta curves obtained before aging and after 60 days of aging for both Scenarios and both aging conditions, illustrating the evolution in T_g values.

Fig. 6a and b presents the evolution of the T_g values in Scenario 1 for the cases of hydrothermal and weathering aging, respectively, while Fig. 6c and d presents the evolution of T_g values in Scenario 2, for the cases of hydrothermal and weathering aging, respectively.

For all test intervals, the calculated standard deviation of T_g mean values highlighted a minimal deviation. The T_g values evolution observed in hydrothermal aging is different than during weathering, confirming the different impact of both environments and therefore different mechanisms of degradation. Notably, water erosion was also

present during weathering, enabling possible hydrothermal degradation mechanisms occurring simultaneously.

With regards to hydrothermal aging in Scenario 1 (Fig. 6a), a decrease in the T_g values was observed until 30 days of aging duration, while a substantial increase was observed between 30 and 45 days of aging, leading to a T_g close to that of the reference value before aging. For the case of weathering aging in Scenario 1 (Fig. 6b), the mean T_g values showed a slight, continuous decrease for the aging intervals of 15, 30, and 45 days, reaching a drop of 4.81 % compared to the reference value. After 45 days of aging, T_g values showed a marginal increase, reaching a mean T_g value close to that of the reference material after 60 days of aging.

The two aging environments showed different impacts on the kinetics of degradation of the material, for both Scenario 1 and 2. In the case of Scenario 2, for hydrothermal aging (Fig. 6c), the impact of aging is equivalent to the effect of reprocessing, but in opposite directions. In this case, an increase in the T_g values is observed during aging, meaning that the internal polymer's structure is more cohesive than the reference's one. This may be explained by the ester bonds breaking during

Fig. 7. Representative tensile testing curves for both Scenarios 1 & 2 and environmental aging conditions.

Fig. 8. Mechanical properties evolution for both Scenarios 1 and 2 and environmental aging conditions.

aging [31,58,65], which may facilitate hydrogen bond formation and therefore reinforce the polymer structure. On the other hand, the decrease observed during reprocessing may be attributed to the thermomechanical shear forces applied during reprocessing, which could potentially break the hydrogen bonds previously formed during aging.

In contrast to hygrothermal aging in *Scenario 2*, weathering combined with reprocessing (Fig. 6d) exhibits a lower impact from aging compared to the reprocessing cycles. As can be seen in Fig. 6d, T_g values change significantly after the first and second reprocessing iterations (see arrows on the graph). At the same time, the aging does not significantly impact the T_g values. The impact of weathering is also lower in *Scenario 2* (Fig. 6d) than in *Scenario 1* (Fig. 6b). This can be explained by a homogenization effect resulting from heterogeneous erosion. Heterogeneous erosion occurs when the degradation rate (hydrolysis) is higher than the diffusion rate of water into the sample and is not characterised by volume shrinkage over time, as is the case for homogeneous erosion [39]. Erosion has likely been heterogeneous, as the samples were exposed to external conditions, resulting in higher degradation on the sample's surface than in its internal part.

When comparing hygrothermal aging and weathering in *Scenario 2* (Fig. 6c and d), T_g variations are observed during the reprocessing process, with a predominant impact from the reprocessing in the case of the weathering. The reduction in the T_g values may be attributed to polymer chain scission during the Norrish II reaction, resulting in a less cohesive structure. Regarding the increase in the T_g values during the second reprocessing process but also during the last aging period of *Scenario 1* in weathering (Fig. 6b), this may be attributed to crosslinking phenomena induced by photoionisation.

3.2. Mechanical properties

Through tensile testing, Ultimate Tensile Strength σ_{UTS} , Young's modulus E , and the strain at break ϵ_b values were recorded. Fig. 7 presents representative tensile testing curves, obtained before aging and after 60 days of aging, for both *Scenarios* and both environmental aging conditions.

Fig. 8 presents mechanical properties (E modulus (Young's modulus), Elongation at break and Tensile Strength at break) evolution for both *Scenarios 1* and *2* and aging conditions.

3.2.1. Young's modulus

The mean Young's modulus value (E) was calculated for five tests per condition and plotted as a function of the aging time for all aging and reprocessing intervals. In *Scenario 1* (Fig. 8a and b), both hygrothermal

aging and weathering show a non-linear behaviour. A slight increase in stiffness is observed after 15 days of aging, followed by a decrease until 45 days of aging and a final increase after 60 days of aging. Hygrothermal aging causes more pronounced degradation in E values, with E dropping by 18 % between 15 and 45 days of aging. In contrast, weathering leads to a milder effect, resulting in an ultimate 7 % increase compared to the reference.

In *Scenario 2*, as can be seen in Fig. 8c and d, both aging environments caused a more significant decline in stiffness with a similar impact on the values of E (about 25 % drop at the end of the experiment). This indicates that recycling as a process is the dominant degradation factor when comparing both aging conditions. The evolution curves exhibit a similar pattern: an initial increase in E , a decrease in the second aging period, a recovery around 45 days, and a final decline. Notably, the second reprocessing cycle (after 30 days) has opposite effects in hygrothermal vs weathering conditions, suggesting a strong interaction between reprocessing history and environmental exposure. The decrease in E during reprocessing may be attributed to polymer chain scissions or side group cleavages. These phenomena can be induced by thermomechanical stress during processing and are correlated to the T_g evolution trends observed in hygrothermal aging.

When comparing *Scenario 1* and *2* in hygrothermal aging (Fig. 8a and c), it is worth mentioning that the evolution in stiffness is less prominent than in weathering. This may be attributed to the greater impact of hygrothermal aging on the stiffness values, partially covering the impact of reprocessing. In contrast, in weathering, the effect linked to the reprocessing history appears to dominate, likely due to surface-dominant degradation mechanisms.

With respect to underlying mechanisms, photoionisation reactions take place during weathering and are followed by polymer chain scissions [5] and lead to a higher number of intermolecular reactions than intramolecular reactions. On the contrary, hygrothermal aging leads to non-enzymatic chain scissions followed by chain-end cleavages, thus meaning a higher rate of intramolecular reactions [31,39]. Considering these elements, the results highlight that hygrothermal aging leads to a more profound structural breakdown and, therefore, a significant drop in stiffness. On the other hand, the increase in E at specific aging points in *Scenario 1* may reflect the formation of hydrogen bonds or cross-linking phenomena. In hygrothermal aging, hydrolysis may facilitate the formation of hydrogen bonds and van der Waals interactions, therefore reinforcing the polymer cohesion. In weathering, photo-induced cross-linking may occur to a lesser extent due to the lower polarity of the functional groups formed (enols and alkenes, from Norrish reactions) compared to ester functionalities.

Fig. 9. Transmittance at 1746 cm^{-1} evolution for both Scenarios 1 & 2 and aging environments.

3.2.2. Strain at break ϵ_b

As can be seen from Fig. 8, the values of ϵ_b evolve differently depending on the type of accelerated aging environment. In *Scenario 1* under hygrothermal aging (Fig. 8a), ϵ_b increases by $\sim 20\%$ after 15 days of aging, slightly decreases over the following two aging intervals ($\sim 4\%$ drop) before reaching a 40% increase after 60 days of aging. This suggests that absorbed moisture, prolonged with increasing aging duration, may act as a plasticiser, increasing chain mobility and delaying material fracture. In weathering (Fig. 8b), ϵ_b values increase up to 17% at 30 days of aging before ultimately dropping to a value close to that of the reference. The initial increase in the ϵ_b a possible crosslinking may support values, while the consecutive drop may be attributed to the polymer chain scissions induced through the Norrish II reaction [5,66].

In *Scenario 2*, hygrothermal aging (Fig. 8c) engenders a significant decrease in the ϵ_b values during the first reprocessing cycle - leading to a property drop of 40% - while subsequent reprocessing cycles have minimal additional impact. In weathering (Fig. 8d), the combination of reprocessing and accelerated aging leads to a decrease in the ϵ_b values. This observation highlights the combined effect of reprocessing-induced chain scissions and environment-induced photo-oxidative degradation, possibly complicated by the formation of low-polarity groups that reduce intermolecular interactions.

The comparison of *Scenarios 1* and *2* under hygrothermal aging reveals the potential plasticising effect of absorbed water, known for PLA, considering its hydrophilicity [30]. The absorbed water may disrupt intermolecular interactions and alter crystallinity, resulting in increased ductility. However, in weathering, the dominance of reprocessing damages prevents this ductility increase.

3.2.3. Tensile strength σ_{UTS}

In *Scenario 1*, σ_{UTS} values decrease by 20% after 60 days of hygrothermal aging (Fig. 8a), while remaining stable under weathering (Fig. 8b). This mirrors the behaviour observed in the evolution of E values and confirms the stronger effect of hygrothermal aging previously observed. Hygrothermal aging, through the chain scission followed by a chain-end cleavage, leads to a faster and more prominent breakage of the polymer chains, and therefore a larger drop in the σ_{UTS} values. The observation made in this case confirms the hypothesis supporting the evolution in E values.

In the case of *Scenario 2*, the evolution of the σ_{UTS} values differ when comparing hygrothermal aging (Fig. 8c) vs. weathering (Fig. 8d), postulating a different impact from the environmental aging factors. As

in *Scenario 1*, hygrothermal aging engenders a more pronounced ultimate degradation with a drop of 48% in the σ_{UTS} values vs a drop of $\sim 22\%$ in weathering. When considering the impact of reprocessing and comparing hygrothermal aging with weathering, opposite behaviours are observed in terms of the impact of reprocessing on hygrothermal aging and weathering. In hygrothermal aging, a 20% drop is observed after the first reprocessing iteration, while an 18% increase in weathering is observed at the same iteration. These behaviours highlight the prominent impact of aging combined to reprocessing of combined aging and reprocessing. Hydrolysis promotes permanent damage while weathering allows for partial recovery through crosslinking phenomena. However, an increasing reprocessing history, combined with environmental conditions, ultimately leads to accelerated failure.

3.3. Chemical characterisation

Chemical characterisation was employed to scrutinise the background mechanisms manifested as changes in mechanical properties. Chemical characterisation involved FT-IR and GPC analyses, with a view to studying the evolution of the oxidation of the material as well as its molecular weight.

3.3.1. Transmittance at 1746 cm^{-1} – secondary carbonyl species

For FT-IR, the mean values of the transmittance at 1746 cm^{-1} (T_{1746}) were assessed and plotted as a function of the aging time (Fig. 9).

In *Scenario 1* (Fig. 9a and b), a decreasing tendency in the T_{1746} absorbance values was observed during aging, indicating an increase in the concentration of secondary carbonyl species due to degradation. In hygrothermal aging (Fig. 9a), the decrease follows a linear trend with an average drop of $\sim 5\%$ after each aging cycle, resulting in an ultimate reduction of 24% . In contrast, for weathering (Fig. 9b), the evolution pattern is non-linear, exhibiting a decrease of 8% after 15 days of aging, followed by a plateau until 45 days of aging and an ultimate more pronounced decrease leading to a final drop of about 20% .

Despite showcasing different kinetics, both environments lead to similar overall degradation after 60 days of aging. The decrease in T_{1746} is consistent with hydrolytic and photo-oxidative degradation mechanisms previously mentioned, where ester bond cleavage may lead to carbonyl end groups formation [7,66]. However, while both aging environments engender ester scission, the mechanisms differ. In hygrothermal aging, the presence of water accelerates hydrolysis and facilitates the formation of carboxylic acid and aldehyde end groups. In

Fig. 10. Mn, Mw and PDI evolution for both Scenarios 1 & 2 and aging environments.

weathering, photo-induced Norrish reactions also generate secondary carbonyl species, but in a lesser concentration and often with surface-limited effects.

In *Scenario 2*, and for both aging conditions (Fig. 9c and d), the combination of aging and reprocessing is found to have a less pronounced effect on T_{1746} than *Scenario 1*. Indeed, the maximum variation is about 7 %, while up to 25 % variation due to reprocessing was observed for mechanical properties. A dilution effect may explain this smaller chemical variation. Degradation products initially concentrated at the sample surface are homogenised during reprocessing, mixing with less-degraded inner regions and leading to a decrease in apparent carbonyl concentration. This hypothesis aligns with the increase in transmittance (i.e., reduction in T_{1746} absorbance) observed only during reprocessing steps. Thus, from a chemical perspective, reprocessing appears to reduce the detectability of aldehyde/ketone groups, either by diluting surface degradation or breaking these groups under thermal and mechanical stress. This aligns with studies highlighting that thermo-mechanical degradation during reprocessing engenders chain scission and random backbone breakdown, resulting in the cleavage of previously formed carbonyl-containing end groups [10,45].

3.3.2. Molecular weight – Mn and Mw

The molecular weight evolution was evaluated through values of number average molecular weight (Mn), weight average molecular weight (Mw) and polydispersity index (PDI), as indicators of polymer structure evolution and were plotted as a function of the aging time (Fig. 10).

In *Scenario 1* (Fig. 10a and b), a general decrease in Mn and Mw is observed for both aging environments. The decrease is more severe in hydrothermal aging, with values dropping by about 20 % vs 8 % in the case of weathering after 60 days of aging. These results are consistent with the evolution of mechanical and chemical properties, where hydrothermal aging leads to a greater structural breakdown. For PDI , hydrothermal aging initially causes a decrease until 30 days of aging, followed by an increase and then a decrease, resulting in an ultimate value close to the reference value. Similarly to Mn and Mw evolutions, the PDI is less severely impacted by weathering than by hydrothermal aging, suggesting an initial phase of uniform degradation followed by heterogeneous scission and chain recombination or branching. In contrast, weathering induces minimal variation in PDI , pointing to less aggressive, more surface-restricted degradation.

These observed behaviours are consistent with the literature, where

Södergård & Stolt, among others, reported that end-group hydrolysis is predominant during hydrolytic degradation of PLA, translated by a similar decrease of Mn and Mw and a PDI impacted negatively [7,30,31, 67]. This confirms that water diffuses into the polymer matrix, cleaving ester bonds and leading to uniform molecular weight reduction [67]. The reduced variability of the PDI in weathering also shows that there is a less aggressive mechanism of hydrolytic degradation, supported by the fact that the polymer was not immersed, as in hydrothermal aging. Such a lowered molecular weight loss could be attributed to the slowed oxidative/photo-degradation of PLA, which is surface-controlled and evolves more slowly under the weathering conditions used [68,69].

In *Scenario 2* (Fig. 10c and d), reprocessing has a more substantial impact than aging. The main deterioration comes from the reprocessing step itself, negatively impacting the Mn and Mw values by 5–15 %, while the aging process itself affects the Mn and Mw values by a maximum of 7 %. The evolutions of Mn , Mw and PDI are consistent with the literature and the reported effects of thermo-mechanical stresses induced during reprocessing, leading to random chain scission during recycling, observed through the decrease of Mw , Mn , and the main decrease of PDI during the reprocessing [7,24,45]. The PDI evolution, however, exhibits different behaviour when comparing the two aging conditions. In hydrothermal aging, the PDI is negatively impacted by the aging process, with a minimal impact from the reprocessing steps, suggesting end-group hydrolysis as the dominant degradation mechanism, as mentioned for *Scenario 1*. In contrast, under weathering, a more critical decrease is observed during the reprocessing steps and is balanced by a slight increase during the aging process. The initial rise in PDI conforms to the occurrence of random chain scission during reprocessing, leading to a higher molecular weight distribution [10,70,71].

Overall, the trends in Mn , Mw , and PDI across both scenarios reflect the complex interplay between aging environment and processing history. Hydrothermal conditions cause uniform internal degradation, while weathering induces surface-level changes. Reprocessing, on the other hand, introduces random scission through thermal and shear stresses and redistributes degradation by mixing surface and core, altering both molecular and chemical profiles.

4. Conclusion

This work studied potential synergic effects and cumulative property degradation patterns occurring during the use and EoL phases of PLA material throughout two different *Scenarios*. *Scenario 1*, corresponded to

Fig. 11. Summary of properties evolution for both Scenarios 1&2 and aging environments.

a single use of a plastic material, and *Scenario 2*, simulated multiple uses of a plastic product, combining iterative cycles of accelerated aging, reprocessing and remanufacturing. Fig. 11 summarises the evolution of the studied properties for the two studied *Scenarios*.

Key findings of this work are:

- Hydrothermal aging induced more severe degradation than weathering across all mechanical, chemical and physical properties studied, due to enhanced hydrolytic scission of ester bonds.
- Reprocessing significantly affected PLA structure, as observed on microscope and CT-scan pictures and translated through the different properties' evolution. Particularly, a greater impact was observed on Mn, Mw and strain at break. However, its influence on secondary carbonyl species concentration was minimal, possibly acting as a homogeniser of surface degradation.
- Chemical properties evolution was shown to be slower than mechanical properties evolution, while following a similar trend, reinforcing the role of water in ester hydrolysis under both aging environments.
- The combined effects of aging and reprocessing in *Scenario 2* revealed a synergistic degradation pattern, with the predominant effect of thermo-mechanical stresses, jointly accelerating the decrease in mechanical properties and chain scissions.

Scenario 2 revealed a more significant impact of hydrothermal aging, already observed to a lesser extent in Scenario 1, with reprocessing no longer possible after 4 cycles in the case of hydrothermal aging.

- The structure of the printed samples was affected negatively by the increased number of reprocessing and aging cycles. The authors couldn't determine in this study to what extent the degradation in mechanical properties was linked to the material's degradation itself and the sample quality, but also to the polymer's degradation.
- The presence/addition of additives and stabilisers, which could enhance the lifetime of the reprocessed polymer and help with further recycling and use, was not considered.

In summary, this study confirms the presence of a synergic effect when combining accelerated aging and reprocessing. This highlights the importance of performing accelerated aging studies combined with EoL simulation to reproduce the real service life of a plastic product,

allowing to study their influence on original material properties. Therefore, the findings of this study are of particular importance for manufacturing and recycling industries, throughout the transition to the circular era, which considerably increases the market need for more 'recycled' plastic volumes.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Floriane Verceux: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Sotirios Grammatikos:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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